

THE SITUATION IN THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN IS ABOUT TO START A NEW STAGE OF REFORMS

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Abstract: This article talks about the situation and its condition in the preschool education system of Uzbekistan on the eve of the new stage of reforms.

Key words: upbringing, education, theory, On-line, modern education, methods, scientific research, level of knowledge, preschool education.

Enter. The development of education in the world is much faster than in other areas. This opinion is confirmed by the fact that many countries of the world, including Uzbekistan, conduct scientific research on the educational system and its place and role in personnel training. Today, education in Uzbekistan is traditional, part-time and part-time, modern and all The wide use of inclusive, on-line, distance education, open and flexible forms of education is becoming very important.

In recent years, in our country, education of the young generation, further development of the education system, scientific fields, and production of potential personnel have become one of the most important directions of the state policy.

Today, the field of education is one of the most important and sensitive aspects of our society. A series of reforms being carried out in this regard, including the state policy on youth education and their activities, is an important and urgent task of the day. So, this issue by itself requires serious attention to be paid to a number of problems related to the education system in our country.

The primary, most basic link of continuing education is the preschool education system. According to the scientific conclusions of experts, a person receives 70% of all the information and information he receives during his life before the age of 5. This fact alone clearly shows how important the education and training received in the preschool educational institution is for our children to grow up as mature and well-rounded individuals.

Analysis and results. Pre-school education institutions during the time of the Soviets consisted of kindergartens and nurseries. Babies from 3 to 6 years of age were included in them and brought up in the spirit of communist ideology. These institutions served well as an important support for busy parents in production. In addition to cities, kindergartens were opened in rural areas and they carried out pre-school education. But not all young children were able to receive kindergarten education, they mostly grew up at home.

In the context of the crisis of the union, the number of kindergartens has decreased sharply, and the funds necessary to ensure their operation have decreased over the years. The number of children's institutions operating at the expense of collective farms and state farms has decreased. Independently, in 1990, there were 4,569 kindergartens in

which 518,500 children were educated. In 1991, there were 4,766 preschool educational institutions and 549,860 children were educated in them, while in 1992, this figure was 4,588 preschool educational institutions (MTM) and 549,131 students. ¹However, there was no growth in the following years. On the contrary, the number of kindergartens and kindergartens decreased year by year possible to regulate the work of pre-school education institutions at once, as in all areas

. Positive processes in this direction began in the late 90s.

The reform of primary education has also begun on the basis of the Law on Education. During the reform period, not only ordinary kindergartens were established, but also specialized homes for raising children. Among them, new educational institutions of the state, non-state and agencies appeared, such as remedial, language, artistic education and sports, children with physical and mental disabilities, private home kindergartens. The experience of their organization and material support was accumulated.

In 2005, 430355 young children were educated in 4366 kindergartens.

To them 4 31533 higher and medium qualified coaches mentored . Unfortunately, the network of kindergartens and kindergartens, and the number of teachers and students in them, decreased even during the period of the reforms in the period of independence. Comparing the statistical data of 2006-2007 and 2011-2012 academic years, it can be seen that the number of kindergartens decreased from 4358 to 3263, the number of students from 325668 to 220614, and the number of educators from 43104 to 7637.²

The facts show that due to the sharp reduction in the number of kindergartens and the decrease in the number of working places, a social environment has emerged where women stay at home and raise their children by themselves. This situation prompted the emergence of private and home kindergartens. Some of them were opened in the place of old kindergartens that were taken out of state ownership and found new owners based on auctions.

Due to the increase in the variety of services and the amount, the fees in these educational institutions were slightly higher than in public institutions. The education and health administration staff were also responsible for the systematic provision of private kindergartens and the healthy growth of children.

If we refer to statistical data, while the number of kindergartens in many cities remains almost unchanged, only 1-2 small children's institutions are working in district centers and large villages. Most of them organized their activities at the expense of funds paid by parents. Such a situation was characteristic of the whole of Uzbekistan and indicated the need to reform the system. As a practical proof of this, we can show that by 2016, the number of preschool educational institutions has decreased to 3249.

2014 - In accordance with the "Year of a Healthy Child" state program, the Ministry of Public Education published for the first time 5 books on preparing children for school for parents: "Speech development, reading and literacy", "Formation of mathematical ideas", "Collection of poetic works". A collection of prose works", "Healthy body - healthy mind" manuals were created. These manuals are intended for parents whose children are not included in the pre-school education system, with the help of which the child's worldview,

¹Statistical collection of the 15th anniversary of Uzbekistan's independence . - 2006. - B. 194.

²Statistical collection of the 15th anniversary of Uzbekistan's independence . - 2006. - B. 19 8 .

logical thinking and speech are developed, and they are introduced to the rules of personal hygiene.

The manuals were prepared in a colorful form on the basis of the "Bolajon" basic program and were approved by the scientific council of the Republican Educational Methodology Center for retraining and professional development of preschool educational institutions.

Pre-school education planners of the departments of methodical support and organization of public education institutions in all regions of the republic, together with representatives of the "Mahalla" charity public fund and other partner organizations and agencies, formed a list of families with 5-7-year-old children who are not included in pre-school education, and provided them with manuals through school libraries. distributed for free. Parents, using the manual throughout the year, began to prepare their child for school education.

In pre-school educational institutions, foreign languages were taught in a playful manner, in accordance with the age and outlook of the children. Kindergarten children have mastered basics such as counting, self-introduction, days of the week, and seasons in a foreign language. At the same time, problems and shortcomings were allowed in the reforms in the education system. "The first task is in the field of pre-school education," said the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev, "We must openly admit that we neglected work in this important field."³

Summary. In fact, one of the biggest and most urgent problems in this area is the inclusion of preschool children in preschool educational institutions. If we look at the time before independence, in particular, in the mid-80s in the republic, 39 percent of children were enrolled in preschool education institutions. Of course, according to this indicator, the Republic of Uzbekistan was far behind the level of the Union (57 percent). Difficulties in the early years of independence led to further deterioration of this indicator. In 1991, coverage of children under 1-6 years of age in preschools decreased from 35.1 percent to 17.3 percent in 2016. In the regions, it decreased from 40.8 percent in 1991 to 13.9 percent by 2016. Only by 2017, this indicator increased slightly and made 22.5 percent.⁴

In 1991, there were 5456 MTMs operating in the republic, but by 2016 their number had decreased to 3251. As of January 1, 2018, this figure was 3253. The low level of education of educators and many other problems also led to this situation

³Mirziyoev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility are the activities of every leader should be a daily rule. — T.: Uzbekistan, 2017. – B. 45.

⁴Uzbekistan Republic of the State Statistics Committee No. 01/2-01-19-84 dated January 19, 2018 gave information based on prepared .

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